

METHODOLOGY OF INSTRUCTION PREPARATION IN MOTHER TONGUE TEACHING

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Abstract: This article talks about what kind of exhibits the teacher should use in the process of teaching the mother tongue. In order to attract the attention of students, recommendations are given on how and in what form visual aids should be.

Key words: "sword" chain, films, photos, communication, analysis of problems or questions, goal location and technologies, teaching students to read the rules of imagination, strengthening students' intellectual and visionary process.

The main recommendation for instructional preparation in mother tongue teaching is as follows:

1. Prepare the instruction for learners in a chain of "doing". This means that it shows a history of each step that you have learned and executed in the sequence of instructions that should be followed during each step. This method allows learners to understand the instruction and follow the steps correctly.
2. Instructions make instructions simple, complex, and concise for learners. Do not use videos, photos, or objects that are difficult to view that show the instruction itself and show it to others.
3. Guidelines are a key part of the support contract for embedded learners, meaning learners are not told how, where and how much support they want.
4. The instructions should not be a mastered schedule, as some learners may find the tasks in the schedule confusing
5. Learners should be required to clearly understand a consistent definition of the teacher and instruction. Learners can get help from the purpose of the instruction, the problems, the methods, and the follow-up work.
6. The guide should provide a wide range of problem-solving skills.
7. It is necessary to communicate with the students when the instructions are given and to talk about them. This is necessary for learners to analyze the comprehensible aspect of the instruction and can aid in their comprehension and problem solving.

What kind of support do you provide for preparing guidelines?

1. Analysis of problems or questions - Before preparing instructions for teaching in the educator's instruction, it is necessary to analyze problems or questions. The description requirements of these target questions are prepared according to the techniques and methods of analyzing the students' broad understanding of the tasks given in the instruction.
2. The method of preparing instruction in education will be updated as the place of purpose and technologies - the society is expanded. The purpose of this is to bring students to reinforce their learning by analyzing specific problems or questions. To create such a goal,

students must be taught certain technologies and methods. Technologies allow you to write visual or imaginary rules for instructional preparation.

3. Teaching students to read the rules of imagination - In order to make reading useful for students, the methodology of teaching instruction should be designed to teach them to read the rules of imagination. Problems or questions in this guide may indicate that the techniques for creating the guide are viewable.

4. Enhancing the students' intellectual and visual process - In the preparation of the instruction, an effort is made to allow each student to improve his reading ability by writing imaginative notes. This helps to strengthen, clarify and limit the intellectual and visual processes of students.

5. Show students how to apply it to real-world activities - When preparing instruction, practice tests should be given to reinforce what students see in practice. This test can be written by the teacher and approved, where the students can also help him strengthen his visual and intellectual skills by showing him the correct answers.

6. Broadly Teach Financial and Experiential Learning Methods - Teacher preparation is designed to improve students' critical goals by teaching financial and experiential learning methods. These methods make it interesting and challenging for students to learn to cover a wider range of management, discussion, scheduling and other areas.

7. Training for teachers - Instructional training methodology provides great additional compliance and training for teachers. This will help him/her to make instruction fun, create instructions, create guides, and improve teaching methods.

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